

Job Satisfaction of Intermediate Level College Teachers

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Abstract

The teaching is one of the prestigious jobs and plays a distinctive role in national development. The objectives of the study were to analyze the intense feeling of college teachers of Dinajpur district concerning the factors of job satisfaction. The study was based on primary and secondary data sources. The primary data were collected through a well-structured questionnaire with 21 items based on five point Likert scale. One open ended questionnaire was given to the respondents. Secondary data were collected from published referred journals. The study was designed on the basis of snowball sampling procedure. The questionnaire were distributed almost all the teachers of four colleges and out of them 49 fill up properly. The data were analyzed by MS-Excel program. Apparently, 70% respondents are satisfied with the behavior of colleagues and section head. Moreover, nearly 50%-70% employees are satisfied with working areas, chance to do work, tasks variations, importance in work, competence of section head, integrity of peers, chance to do something for others and give suggestions, chance to use potentials and work with own style, working conditions, praise of works, and feelings of accomplishment. Besides, teachers are dissatisfied with employment, opportunity in job, own judgment, organizational policy, and pay & salary. The study suggests that the college authority should be very affirmative to the young employees by means of generating creative working environment, freedom in work, and more benefits to enhance their level of job satisfaction.

Keywords: Satisfaction, College, Employee, Job, Teaching

IJSB

Accepted 21 August 2019
Published 22 August 2019
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.3374403

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Introduction

Job satisfaction is the full contentment of someone which indicates the peacefulness of a person's attitude. Job satisfaction is the attitude of an employee to do work with commitment, pleasure and unambiguous in nature (Sapna and Gabha, 2013). The teachers pass most of their time in a college. Their satisfaction may come from different aspects of the job like what they get, how they think, what they wants, why they don't get etc. In analyzing different factors it may vary from person to person. Some opportunities must open to the employees who work in their organization. Job satisfaction is a positive impression of someone that shown in one's own face spontaneously. Teachers play vital role in a college and obviously for national development. A teacher needs safety, gratitude, new knowledge and freedom. Job is not only a main source of income but also an important component of life (George et. al., 2008). Job satisfaction has the ability to meet teachers need and improve their teaching performance. The teachers perform well when they are satisfied. Suki (2011) examined the effect of gender on employee perception of job satisfaction and organizational commitment has no significant effect and commitment comes from job satisfaction. Sometimes, Job satisfaction of employees depends whether the organization is govt. or non-govt. Mehta (2012) found that there is a significance difference in the level of job satisfaction of govt. and private school teachers. The mean score for female teacher was higher than male teacher during times of burnout for developing a test on burnout and its effects on job satisfaction and organizational commitment (Nagar, 2012). Therefore, job satisfaction is inevitable part of teaching career. The satisfaction is imperative in all aspects of any profession; the occurrence of skills, knowledge and competencies depends upon the satisfaction of behavior of individuals (Kumari and Jafri, 2002). So, it is vital that available opportunities are to be granted. Otherwise it may cause employee dissatisfaction, turnover and absenteeism. A satisfied employee is an asset of any organization. Job satisfaction ensures employees responsibility in a good manner and it retain the present employees in their own position and attract other employees toward accomplishing organization goals. A teacher is a backbone of a nation. So, proper facilities should be provided to the teachers like training, allowance, refreshment, research etc. If they get these than they will work in full motion and committed toward achieving an organization goals.

Review of literature

Job satisfaction is unavoidable for all kinds of services. Teacher job satisfaction, according to Griffith (2004), refers to "a teacher's affective relation to his or her teaching role" (p. 605). It replicates how teachers perceive their actual job outcomes in comparison with their desired job outcomes. Research shows a variety of factors that could impact one's job satisfaction, which include, but are not limited to, leadership, peer support, organizational culture, work conditions, promotions, salaries, benefits, relationship with others, etc. (Blegen, 1993; De Loach, 2003; Thyer, 2003; Gigantesco et al., 2003; Koustelios et al., 2003; McNeese-Smith, 1997; Nguni et al., 2006; Navaie-Waliser et al., 2004; Rad & Yarmohammadian, 2006; Rice & Schneider, 1994; Ilies & Judg, 2003; Bruk-Lee et al., 2009; Judge et al., 2002). Components that may influence teachers' activity fulfillment in school have been in the spotlight for certain years and there have been different activities and changes targeting expanding instructor work fulfillment, which appears to be never satisfying the desires sought after by instructors themselves. That brings up issues about how to characterize instructor work fulfillment, and what variables may impact it? The writing extends to numerous definitions with respect to employment opportunity fulfillment that have been inexactly utilized and characterized in various ways. When all is said in done, job satisfaction is seen as

representatives' passionate status responded from the examination of their professional adventures. (Locke, 1976; Nguni et al., 2006; Rad & Yarmohammadian, 2006). Personality profile affiliation may also be associated with teachers' job satisfaction. Indication shows that teachers with high positive affectivity report greater job satisfaction (Badri et al., 2013; Lent et al., 2011). Teacher job satisfaction can be importantly enhanced if teachers have higher commit to their jobs, recommending that school principals should create conditions to increase teacher self-ability for the improvement of their job satisfaction. In this procedure, while teachers have displayed an unavoidable and amazing workforce, school authority could impact teachers' work demeanor and self-adequacy by methods for a collective and distributive administration approach that is bound to educator self-viability, responsibility and occupation fulfillment. The discoveries from this examination along these lines include the inside and out examination educators' points of view of how disseminated administration may influence instructor self-viability and job satisfaction. Nguni et al. (2006), who directed a study on primary school teachers in Tanzania, examining the effects of leadership on teacher job satisfaction. They argued that job satisfaction served as a mediator for the impacts of transformational leadership on other consequences such as teachers' organization commitment and organizational citizenship behaviors. Most of the teacher feel engaged whenever they participate in the decision making process of the institution. Studies on factors that may have affected teacher job satisfaction have revealed that teacher job satisfaction is, in particular, associated with whether, and to what extent, teachers get involved in the decision-making process in schools (Al-Yaseen & Al-Musaileem, 2015; Amzat & Idris, 2012; Alutto & Belasco, 1973; Bademo & Tefera, 2016; Flannery, 1980; Mohrman et al., 1978; Sukirno & Siengthai, 2011). Literature proved that for getting better output of the teachers organization cannot think with the environment of job satisfaction. Though teaching profession is totally based on psychological efforts, organizational commitment, and leadership, therefore, this profession is highly connected to job satisfaction and job engagement.

The objectives of the study were to analyze the job satisfaction of intermediate level college teacher in extent to gender, age, experience, and job position and nature of the organization. Additionally, to see the intense feeling of college teacher of Dinajpur district regarding their working environment, co-workers behavior, authority and other factors of job satisfaction. In past, many researches were held in the field of job satisfaction. There is a scarce of research in job satisfaction of intermediate level teachers especially in Bangladesh. This study is an endeavor to fulfill that scarcity. The study based on the data of four colleges of Dinajpur district more specifically in town areas that may result in narrow conclusion. Sometimes, it is found that the teachers are not willing to give their job satisfaction data and some are very reluctant about the matter. In a word, they are not mindful about their job satisfaction that create hinder in data collection.

Methodology of the study

The study was based on primary and secondary data sources. The primary data was collected through a well-structured questionnaire. The questionnaire was designed on the basis of the short form of Minnesota satisfaction questionnaire (Weiss et. al., 1967) with 21 items based on five point Likert scale from 1 = very dissatisfied to 5 = very satisfied (Likert, 1932). Some demographic information were also collected are age, gender, job position and job experience. One open ended questionnaire was given to the respondent. The study collects their intense feelings about job satisfaction which were not written in closed ended

questionnaire set. Secondary data were collected from published referred journals and books to satisfy the justification of the study. The study was designed on the basis of snowball sampling procedure. The questionnaire were distributed almost all the teacher of four college and out of them 49 fill up and back properly. The data were collected from four selected college and specially confined to the teachers who take the class of intermediate students. One of the colleges is Government, one is semi government and the rest two are private college. The data were analyzed by the use of Microsoft-Excel. The data were collected during January-April, 2018.

Analysis and Interpretation

The analysis of the collected data is formatted in accordance with the objectives of the study from the collected data using a tailored questionnaire is presenting one by one in this section.

Table- 1: No of Teacher in Intermediate Section

Name of Colleges	Holy Land College (HLC)	Mount Everest College (MEC)	Dinajpur Govt. College (DGC)	KBM College (KBM)	Total
No of teachers	45	15	50	32	142
Questionnaire distributed	36	15	42	30	123
Data Collection	11	14	08	16	49
Nature of organization	Private College	Private College	Government College	Semi-Govt. College	--

Source: Author's field survey and college database

In the table, we see the no of teachers in different colleges. Among the teachers there are 49 teachers in total who fill-up the questionnaire paper properly and the respondents in different colleges are HLC-11, MEC-14, DGC-08, and KBM-16. There are two private colleges, one government, and one Semi-government College.

Table- 2: Gender and colleges

Name of Colleges	HLC	MEC	DGC	KBM	Total
Male	9	7	6	12	34
Female	2	7	2	4	15
Total	11	14	08	16	49

Source: Author's field survey

In the above table we see that the no of male and female teachers in different colleges. Total female respondents are 15 and total male respondents are 34. So, total no of respondents 49 in number. In HLC there are 9 male and 2 female teachers. In MEC there are equal no of male and female teachers. In DGC there are 6 male and 2 female teachers and the last KBM male respondents are 12 and female respondents are 4.

Table- 3: Age and job satisfaction score

Age range	24-35	36-50	50-Above	Total
Respondents	29	13	7	49
Job satisfaction score	3.33	3.45	3.44	3.38

Source: Author's field survey

From Table- 3 we see that the respondents age range and job satisfaction range. In 24 to 35 age range there are 29 respondents whose job satisfaction score is 3. 33. In 36 to 50 age range

there are 13 respondents their job satisfaction score is 3.45 and in the range of 50 to above there are 7 respondents whose job satisfaction score is 3.44. In these tables it reflects that the job satisfaction level in the age range 24 to 35 is less than the two range table. Because, in that age new comers are first enter into the job. So, they are not fully satisfied. They expect better opportunity and try to search other job. So, their satisfaction level is less than the middle aged people. In 36 to 50 age range their job satisfaction is neither high nor less. Because, they are not quit their job and there is a limited chance to change their job in other organization. These peoples age are crossed to enter into a new job. So, they try and remain happy in their present job. There is less opportunity to leave the organization. Therefore they are satisfied and retain their present job. But in the age range 50 to above they are satisfied on an average job satisfaction score 3.44. Because, they start their job before 30 years ago, they love their present organization; they adjust all hurdles of their working environment. So, overall they are satisfied. In these tables, we see that, in the total job satisfaction figure is not good as well.

Table- 4: Experience and job satisfaction score

Experience	below 2 years	2 to 10 years	above 10 years	Total
Respondents	19	16	14	49
Job satisfaction score	3.44	3.25	3.45	3.38

Source: Author's field survey

In the above table no-4, it is clear that the respondents below 2 years experienced employees are 19 in number. In 2 to 10 years experienced there are 16 respondents. And In 10 years or more experienced employees were 14 respondents respectively. Job satisfaction in 2 to 10 years experienced is less than the other categories. Because, the respondents experience is used in other organization in that situation is a chance to quit job easily, so they are dissatisfied. They have some opportunity to get a good job that makes them dissatisfied. In the figure, we see that below 2 years experienced people are satisfied because they are very new in the organization. They hope that, they get better opportunity in future so they are satisfied. They expect organization make them creative. Also, they have some dream which they fulfill and have a nice future so they are satisfied to their present job. The experienced person who exceeds 10 years or more in an organization is satisfied in nature. Because, they known the organization fully. They have no option to leave the job quickly. Also, they get benefit and other facilities. So, they are satisfied. We know that old is gold. So, they treated gold in an organization. Organization cannot leave these experienced human resources because they are the asset of an organization. They increase the goodwill and capacity of any college.

Table- 5: Nature of the organization and job satisfaction score

Nature of the organization	Govt.	Semi-Govt.	Private	Total
Respondents	8	16	25	49
Job satisfaction score	3.43	3.43	3.33	3.38

Source: Author's field survey

In the table no-5, we see that the nature of the respondent's organizations and their job satisfaction score. It is clear that, government and semi government employees job satisfaction score is high than that of private sectors because government job holders have a secured job and some benefits like fringe benefits, bonuses etc. But in private colleges these benefits are totally uncertain. If the authority wishes then they give up otherwise not. So,

private job holders are tensed in most of the time for their job. It creates dissatisfaction, which influence them badly in their personal as well as service life.

Table- 6: Job satisfaction score of employees on different college

Colleges	Item Range	HLC	MEC	DGC	KBM
Male	Average from item (1 to 20)	3.13	3.51	3.52	3.46
	Overall from item no 21	3.78	3.86	3.33	3.83
Female	Average from item (1 to 20)	2.82	3.55	3.15	3.33
	Overall from item no 21	3.50	3.86	3.00	4.00

Source: Author's field survey

In the table we see that averagely HLC job satisfaction score is narrow than other in both male and female teachers, the main reason is that they cannot apply their own teaching method and style organization persuade them. But in MEC overall the teachers are satisfied than KBM though their salary is less. In DGC and KBM we see that, overall they are satisfied. Both male and female employees are also satisfied.

Table- 7: Job satisfaction score of employees and their organizational position

Nature of the organization	Lecturer	Assistant Professor	Associate Professor	Professor	Total
Respondents	37	9	1	2	49
Job satisfaction score	3.38	3.40	3.20	3.40	3.38

Source: Author's field survey

In the table no 7 we see that, there were 37 Lecturers, 9 Assistant Professor, 1 Associate Professor, and 1 Professor and the total respondents are 49. Analyzing these data we see that job satisfaction score of Assistant Professor and Professor Level is high and others is medium. Finally, total job satisfaction score is below 3.5 but overall they are satisfied.

From the Table-8 and Figure-1, overall they are feel about their present job is satisfied. So, the total score is 3.73. The job satisfaction score for the item no. 5, 6, 9, 18 and 19 are above 3.6. Employees feel about their present job is highest in score. It implies near to satisfy the employees. From the above table the job satisfaction score in the item no. 1, 3, 4, 11 and 16 are above 3.6. Average they are satisfied. From the above table we see that, the job satisfaction score for the item no. 2, 7, 12, 15, 17 and 20 is below 3.4 but above 3.00. In the above figure it was shown that, the item no. 8, 13 and 14 average score of job satisfaction is below 3. So, they are not satisfied in their present job.

Though the questionnaire have used five point likert scale but the result collapsed into three compartments are satisfied (satisfied plus strongly satisfied), dissatisfied (dissatisfied plus strongly dissatisfied), and neutral and some rigorous result found from Figure-2 and Table-8. Overall, almost 78% respondents are satisfied. More than 70% respondents are satisfied with the behavior of colleagues and departmental head, item no. 5 and 18. Employees are mostly dissatisfied with steady employment (42.9% -item no. 8), with the advancement opportunity in job (51%- item no. 14), with freedom to own judgment (34.7%-item no. 15), with company policy (32.7%-item no. 12), and with pay and salary compare to workloads (34.7%-item no. 13). Whereas, almost 50%-70% employees are satisfied with working areas, chance to do work, variety of tasks, get importance in work, competence of section head, decision with the integrity of members, to do something for others, chance to give suggestions, chance to do

something for using potentials, chance to work with own style, working conditions, praise of works, and feelings of accomplishment (item no. 1, 2, 3, 4, 6, 7, 9, 10, 11, 16, 17, 19, and 20).

Table- 8: The level of job satisfaction of the all teachers of all colleges

	On the present job, this is how the respondent feel about	Average score of satisfaction	% of Satisfied	% of Neutral	% of Dissatisfied
1.	Being able to keep busy all the time	3.55	65.3	20.4	14.3
2.	The chance to work alone on the job	3.39	55.1	24.5	20.4
3.	The chance to do different things from time to time	3.45	55.1	24.5	20.4
4.	The chance to be "somebody" in the community	3.49	59.2	26.5	14.3
5.	The way my principal/chairman handles his/her colleagues	3.65	73.5	12.2	14.3
6.	The competence of my chairman in making decisions	3.65	61.2	34.7	4.1
7.	Being able to do things that don't go against my conscience	3.39	55.1	26.5	18.4
8.	The way my job provides for steady employment	2.78	24.5	32.7	42.9
9.	The chance to do things for other people	3.57	65.3	18.4	16.3
10.	The chance to tell people what to do	3.63	69.4	18.4	12.2
11.	The chance to do something that makes use of my abilities	3.53	61.2	20.4	18.4
12.	The way company policies are put into practice	3.08	40.8	26.5	32.7
13.	My pay/salary and the amount of work I do	2.96	36.7	28.6	34.7
14.	The chances for advancement on this job	2.78	30.6	18.4	51.0
15.	The freedom to use my own judgment	3.10	44.9	20.4	34.7
16.	The chance to try my own methods of doing the job	3.45	57.1	24.5	18.4
17.	The working conditions	3.37	49.0	36.7	14.3
18.	The way my colleagues get along with each other	3.61	71.4	18.4	10.2
19.	The praise I get for doing a good job	3.65	67.3	20.4	12.2
20.	The feeling of accomplishment I get from the job	3.47	59.2	26.5	14.3
21.	Overall, how I feel about my present job	3.73	77.6	16.3	6.1

Source: Author's field survey

Figure- 1: Job satisfaction score of all teachers of sample colleges by questionnaire items.

Figure- 2: Job satisfaction level of all teachers of sample colleges by questionnaire items.

Table- 9: Frequency table based on number of observation and percentages

Item No.	Strongly Dissatisfied		Dissatisfied		Neutral		Satisfied		Strongly Satisfied		Total	
	Freq.	%	Freq.	%	Freq.	%	Freq.	%	Freq.	%	Freq.	%
1	1	2.0	6	12.2	10	20.4	29	59.2	3	6.1	49	100
2	1	2.0	9	18.4	12	24.5	24	49.0	3	6.1	49	100
3	0	0.0	10	20.4	12	24.5	22	44.9	5	10.2	49	100
4	0	0.0	7	14.3	13	26.5	25	51.0	4	8.2	49	100
5	2	4.1	5	10.2	6	12.2	32	65.3	4	8.2	49	100
6	0	0.0	2	4.1	17	34.7	26	53.1	4	8.2	49	100
7	1	2.0	8	16.3	13	26.5	25	51.0	2	4.1	49	100
8	3	6.1	18	36.7	16	32.7	11	22.4	1	2.0	49	100
9	0	0.0	8	16.3	9	18.4	28	57.1	4	8.2	49	100
10	0	0.0	6	12.2	9	18.4	31	63.3	3	6.1	49	100
11	0	0.0	9	18.4	10	20.4	26	53.1	4	8.2	49	100
12	1	2.0	15	30.6	13	26.5	19	38.8	1	2.0	49	100
13	3	6.1	14	28.6	14	28.6	18	36.7	0	0.0	49	100
14	2	4.1	23	46.9	9	18.4	14	28.6	1	2.0	49	100
15	1	2.0	16	32.7	10	20.4	21	42.9	1	2.0	49	100
16	1	2.0	8	16.3	12	24.5	24	49.0	4	8.2	49	100
17	1	2.0	6	12.2	18	36.7	22	44.9	2	4.1	49	100
18	1	2.0	4	8.2	9	18.4	34	69.4	1	2.0	49	100
19	0	0.0	6	12.2	10	20.4	28	57.1	5	10.2	49	100
20	0	0.0	7	14.3	13	26.5	28	57.1	1	2.0	49	100
21	0	0.0	3	6.1	8	16.3	37	75.5	1	2.0	49	100

Interpretation from open ended question

The summary of an open ended question that was given to the respondents to know their intense feelings which were not mentioned in the set of 21 items close ended questionnaire. The study summarizes their feelings as follows:

Summary (Evidence from HLC during January to February, 2018):

Contentment brings happiness. In HLC the study analyze the satisfaction level of all the teachers and think that they are not fully satisfied. They think that things do not come to them that way as they want it. Most of the directors are not behave friendly. Job security is not strong enough. They need residential facility, transport and medical facilities. There is not any scope to exercise teachers own thoughts and creative ideas.

Summary (Evidence from MEC during January to February, 2018): In Mount Everest College teachers believe that job satisfaction is correlated with life satisfaction. Unwillingness brings defeat. As a new organization it develops their policies, procedures with teacher friendly. Their running salary is very low because these colleges newly launch their activities but teachers believe that it will increase as time passes. There is an opportunity to apply a teachers own thought and methods. Sometimes, directors behave rudely. But overall as a new college all the teachers are satisfied and hope for the future is bright.

Summary (Evidence from KBM during February to March, 2018): KBM College is the semi-nationalized College there are some problems. Most of the teachers are dissatisfied because they thought that their promotion procedure is very lengthy. Most of the teacher's opinion is that as they are qualified and experienced but they are not selected as a principle or a vice principal. Sometimes they argue that, political influence is more in these colleges. Most of the female teachers are satisfied to their job. They fell proud to be a teacher of KBM College because; it brings their dignity and honor in the society. But most of the male teachers are not satisfied because they mentioned that their salary and other facilities are not adequate also provident fund facilities and after retirement job facilities is not strong enough. Other way overall they are satisfied.

Summary (Evidence from DGC during February to March, 2018): As it is fully Government College so most of the teachers are highly satisfied. But 1 or 2 teacher's think that they are satisfied if the right man will be in the right position and if perfect and qualified man are selected by merit not by power, self- position, and wealth that bring them happiness. Other two teachers noticed that their higher education facilities are not satisfactory. But overall they are satisfied.

Conclusion

Job satisfaction fulfills the expectation of a specific job. It happens when employee feel the necessity of some attributes surrounds to their work. In this study, it is found that most of the respondents are satisfied with their job. More than 70% respondents are satisfied with the behavior of colleagues and departmental head. Furthermore, almost 50%-70% employees are satisfied with working areas, chance to do work, variety of tasks, get importance in work, competence of section head, decision with the integrity of members, to do something for others, chance to give suggestions, chance to do something for using potentials, chance to work with own style, working conditions, praise of works, and feelings of accomplishment. On the contrary, employees are mostly dissatisfied with steady employment, the advancement opportunity in job, freedom to own judgment, organizational policy, and pay & salary compare to workloads. The study also found that most of the employees of these colleges are very young but employees have a less job satisfaction because they are in early stage of career expect a better opportunity and try to search for other job. So, their satisfaction level is less than the others. In two private colleges job is not secured and sometimes the behavior of authority are not conducive that's why they try for alternatives. The study suggests that the college authority should be very positive to the young employees by means of creating

creative working environment, freedom in work, more benefits for additional pressure and career counseling for retaining them.

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Cite this article:

Farhana Rahman (2019). Job Satisfaction of Intermediate Level College Teachers, *International Journal of Science and Business*, 3(1), 204-214.

doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3374403>

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